

Field oriented controlled permanent magnet synchronous motor drive for an electric vehicle

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ABSTRACT

The paper describes field-oriented control strategy with space vector pulse width modulation technique of permanent magnet synchronous motor drive system for an electric vehicle. At first, mathematical models of the motor and the drive system for electric vehicle are presented. In order to obtain high performance drive and maximum motor torque, field-oriented control strategy and space vector pulse width modulation technique method are applied to drive system in next section. Speed controller design utilizing the popular zero-pole elimination approach causes large integral constant time in case of small rotational damping constant. The desired-transient-response-based approach is employed to overcome the problem. Performance indices include overshoot, undershoot, steady-state speed error, and total harmonic distortion of stator current, are employed to assess the drive systems with two speed controller design methods. Theoretical assumptions are confirmed via simulations and criteria in MATLAB/Simulink environment.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EVs) have been playing an important role in achieving allowable carbon levels [1], [2]. Among types of motor, permanent magnet synchronous motors (PMSMs) own suitable characteristics for EVs such as high start-up torque, small torque ripple, built-in magnetic field. For high-performance PMSM drives, direct torque control (DTC) [3]–[5] and field oriented control (FOC) [6]–[10] were utilized. A frame-angle-based DTC for PMSM drives was implemented to get fast and accurate responses at low speeds [3]. An improved DTC with large duty-cycle at transient operation was utilized to achieve fast response [4]. In order to obtain robust transient response, a duty-ratio regulation-based PMSM DTC was employed [5]. The FOC applied to PMSMs provided performance as well as DC motors [6]. The performance of FOC was discussed in drives utilizing hysteresis controller and pulse width modulation (PWM) current controller [7]. Maximum torque was enhanced by injecting current harmonic in FOC drive [8]. A space vector pulse width modulation (SVPWM) technique minimized switching loss in sensorless FOC drive [9]. In order to shorten computing time, a vector space decomposition approach was used in different FOC versions [10]. The FOC was utilized in sensorless drive at high speed [11]. In the paper, the FOC is selected for PMSM drive system of a modeled EV.

In order to ensure constant switching frequency of voltage source inverter (VSI), PWM techniques were utilized [12]–[21]. The SVPWM was implemented into sensorless drives [12]. Total harmonic distortions

(THDs), torque and speed responses, DC link utilization (DCLU) were evaluated for Sinusoidal PWM (SPWM) and SVPWM methods [13]. A PWM technique guaranteed on-time of the low-side switches and decreased capacitor current [14]. The SVPWM replaced for switching sequence selection method to lower torque ripple [15]. An added advantage of SVPWM compared to SPWM was an increase of DCLU [16]. Voltage error was calculated to make switching frequency almost constant [17]. The SVPWM was combined with Kalman filter to lower ripples [18]. A harmonic injecting method increased DCLU [19]. A PWM method lowered loss and current THD [20]. A modulation method shortened time harmonics [21]. For guarantee of constant switching frequency, and better DCLU, the SVPWM is utilized to control the VSI in the paper.

For controllers design of FOC drive, many approaches were presented [22]-[34]. Sliding mode theory and sigmoid function provided robustness of speed controller and chattering elimination [22]. Fuzzy logic speed controller and proportional-integral (PI) current controllers were utilized [23]. MRAC controller accurately provided the actual speed and the rotor position of the PMSM [24]. Design of PI controllers were employed utilizing zero-pole elimination approach for both speed controller and current controllers [25]. Combination of predictive current control and FOC brought improved properties for PMSM drive [26]. For lowering harmonic current, 24-sector vector space decomposition method was implemented [27]. Artificial neural network was inserted into FOC to provide fast response [28]. Adaptive control was applied to control robot-assisted force in FOC drive system [29]. A fractional PI speed controller was used for speed tracking and load rejection performance [30]. Predictive control was assessed in PMSM drive using FOC [31]. Super-twisting sliding mode strategy gave small-overshoot response [32]. Adaptive neuro fuzzy inference mechanism enhanced dynamic performance [33]. Selection of 4-manifolds of stator current provided fast response [34]. In order to obtain linear model of PMSM, an input-output feedback linearization method was applied [35]. The methods listed above are difficult to be implemented on EV. In the paper, a desired transient response-based approach is applied to PI speed controller for simplified model of PMSM drive using SVPWM-FOC.

2. FIELD ORIENTED CONTROL STRUCTURE FOR PMSM DRIVE

Field-oriented-control structure for PMSM drive is shown in Figure 1. The PMSM is mathematically modeled in $\alpha\beta$ stationary reference frame according to (1)-(5).

$$u_{s\alpha} = R_s i_{s\alpha} + \frac{d\psi_{s\alpha}}{dt} \quad (1)$$

$$u_{s\beta} = R_s i_{s\beta} + \frac{d\psi_{s\beta}}{dt} \quad (2)$$

$$\psi_{s\alpha} = L_s i_{s\alpha} + \Phi_F \cos \theta_r \quad (3)$$

$$\psi_{s\beta} = L_s i_{s\beta} + \Phi_F \sin \theta_r \quad (4)$$

$$T_e = 1.5n_p(i_{s\beta}\psi_{s\alpha} - i_{s\alpha}\psi_{s\beta}) \quad (5)$$

Where: $u_{s\alpha}$, $u_{s\beta}$, $i_{s\alpha}$, $i_{s\beta}$, $\psi_{s\alpha}$, $\psi_{s\beta}$ are elements in $\alpha\beta$ frame of stator voltage, current, flux vectors; R_s , L_s - stator resistance, inductance; Φ_F - PM magnetic flux; θ_r - position of rotor; n_p - number of pole pairs. In case of drive for EV, relationship of motor torque T_e , load torque T_L , and mechanical speed ω_m is expressed by (6):

$$T_e = T_L + J_m \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} + B_m \omega_m \quad (6)$$

where J_m - moment of inertia; B_m - rotational damping constant. Parameters of PMSM are listed in Table 1. Clarke Transformation block estimates $\alpha\beta$ stator current elements according to (7)-(8).

$$\hat{i}_{s\alpha} = i_{sa} \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{i}_{s\beta} = \frac{(i_{sa} + 2i_{sb})}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (8)$$

Park transformation block uses (9)-(10) to obtain flux I_d and torque I_q components of stator current:

$$I_d = \hat{i}_{s\alpha} \cos \theta_r + \hat{i}_{s\beta} \sin \theta_r \quad (9)$$

$$I_q = -\hat{i}_{s\alpha} \sin \theta_r + \hat{i}_{s\beta} \cos \theta_r \quad (10)$$

Figure 1. FOC structure for PMSM drive.

Three proportional-integral (PI) controllers including flux-component and torque-component currents, speed one's output reference values of flux u_{sd} and torque u_{sq} components of stator voltages, I_q respectively in Figure 2 according to (11)-(13).

$$u_{sd}^*(s) = K_{pd} \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_{id}s} \right) e_{id}(s) \tag{11}$$

$$u_{sq}^*(s) = K_{pq} \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_{iq}s} \right) e_{iq}(s) \tag{12}$$

$$I_q^*(s) = K_{p\omega} \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_{i\omega}s} \right) e_{\omega}(s) \tag{13}$$

Where K_{pd} , K_{pq} , $K_{p\omega}$; T_{id} , T_{iq} , $T_{i\omega}$ are respectively proportional gains; integral constant times of PI controllers. In order to maximize the torque component current I_q , desired flux component current is chosen to be zero. Inverse Park Transformation block employs position of rotor, desired flux-component and torque-component voltages to obtain desired $\alpha\beta$ stator voltage elements. The SVPWM block uses the desired voltage to obtain switching diagram for IGBTs of three-phase VSI in a switching period.

In order to design PI controllers, block diagrams of control systems are simplified as shown in Figure 2. In case of I_d current control system as shown in Figure 2(a), its transfer function is expressed by (14):

$$G_{Id}(s) = \frac{I_d(s)}{I_d^*(s)} = \frac{K_{pd} \left[\frac{(T_{id}s+1)}{T_{id}s(L_d s + R_s)} \right]}{1 + K_{pd} \left[\frac{(T_{id}s+1)}{T_{id}s(L_d s + R_s)} \right]} \tag{14}$$

The parameters of I_d current controller are chosen as (15) thanks to zero-pole elimination approach [23]:

$$T_{id} = \frac{L_d}{R_s} \tag{15}$$

$$K_{pd} = 2\pi f_d L_d \tag{16}$$

$$f_d = k_f f_s \tag{17}$$

where f_s is switching frequency of the inverter, k_f is selected in range [0.05; 0.2] to minimize THD. The transfer function is written as (18).

$$G_{Id}(s) = \left[(2\pi k_f f_s)^{-1} s + 1 \right]^{-1} \tag{18}$$

Similarly, let K_{pq} , T_{iq} , f_q following (19)-(21) and utilize simple conversions to obtain transfer function of I_q current control system in Figure 2(b) according to (22).

$$T_{iq} = \frac{L_q}{R_s} \tag{19}$$

$$K_{pq} = 2\pi f_q L_q \tag{20}$$

$$f_q = k_f f_s \quad (21)$$

$$G_{Iq}(s) = [(2\pi k_f f_s)^{-1} s + 1]^{-1} \quad (22)$$

In order to obtain transfer function of motor speed control system in Figure 2(c), parameters K_{pd} , T_{id} , L_d , R_s in I_d current control system are respectively substituted by $K_{p\omega}/k_t$, $T_{i\omega}$, J_m , B_m , as follows:

$$T_{i\omega} = \frac{J_m}{B_m} \quad (23)$$

$$K_{p\omega} = 2\pi f_\omega J_m k_t \quad (24)$$

$$G_{\omega m}(s) = [(2\pi f_\omega)^{-1} s + 1]^{-1} \quad (25)$$

$$k_t = \frac{K_T}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{T_N}{(\sqrt{2} I_N)} \quad (26)$$

where K_T is torque constant. Because response times of mechanical systems are longer than electrical systems, f_ω is chosen slower than f_d and f_q :

$$f_\omega = 0.01 f_s \quad (27)$$

The transfer function of speed control system is expressed as (28).

$$G_{\omega m}(s) = [(0.02\pi f_s)^{-1} s + 1]^{-1} \quad (28)$$

In practice, rotational damping constant B_m is small shown in Table 1, this leads to long integral constant time $T_{i\omega}$. So, PI speed controller needs to be redesigned. At first, characteristic equation of speed control system is rewritten as (29).

$$s^2 + \left[\frac{(K_{p\omega} k_t + B_m)}{J_m} \right] s + \frac{K_{p\omega} k_t}{(J_m T_{i\omega})} = 0 \quad (29)$$

Utilizing the method in [36], the stability range of $K_{p\omega}$, $T_{i\omega}$ is the one of $K_{p\omega} > 0$, $T_{i\omega} > 0$. For desired overshoot M_p and settling time t_{set} (decaying exponential reaches 1%), parameters of PI speed controller are computed as follows [37]:

$$\zeta = \sqrt{\frac{(\ln M_p^*)^2}{\pi^2 + (\ln M_p^*)^2}} \quad (30)$$

$$\omega_n = \frac{-\ln 0.01}{\zeta t_{set}^*} \quad (31)$$

$$K_{p\omega} = \frac{(2\zeta \omega_n J_m - B_m)}{k_t} \quad (32)$$

$$T_{i\omega} = \frac{k_t K_{p\omega}}{(J_m \omega_n^2)} \quad (33)$$

where ζ : damping ratio, ω_n : undamped natural frequency.

Table 1. Parameters of PMSM

Symbol	Quantity	Value	Symbol	Quantity	Value
P_N	Rated power	3.9 kW	n_N	Rate speed	3000 rpm
U_N	Rated voltage	180 V	n_p	Number of pole pairs	3
T_N	Rated torque	12.5 Nm	Φ_f	PM magnetic flux	0.185 Wb
I_N	Rated current	14.9 A	R_s	Stator resistance	0.3 Ω
J_m	Motor inertia	0.0755 kgm ²	L_q, L_d	q -axis, d -axis inductances	8.5 mH
B_m	Rotational damping constant	0.001 Nm.s			

Figure 2. Block diagram of control systems: (a) I_d current, (b) I_q current, and (c) motor speed

3. SIMULATION

The MATLAB/Simulink simulations are implemented in cases of $U_{dc} = 440 \text{ V}$, $k_f = 0.08$, $\omega_{m,ref} = \{3000 \text{ rpm}, 300 \text{ rpm}, 30 \text{ rpm}\}$, load torque $T_L = 10 \text{ Nm}$ activated at 2 second time for two methods: first one is the zero-pole elimination approach with $K_{p\omega} = 56.28$, $T_{i\omega} = 75.5 \text{ s}$ (in (23)-(24)) and second one is the desired-transient-response-based approach with desired $M_p = 0.01$ and $t_{set} = 0.1 \text{ s}$, $K_{p\omega} = 11.72$, $T_{i\omega} = 29.6 \text{ ms}$ (31)-(34). Parameters of I_d and I_q controllers are respectively computed according to (15)-(16) and (19)-(20). Outputs of speed controller, current controllers are limited in $\pm 21.1 \text{ A}$, $\pm 255 \text{ V}$, respectively.

Figures 3-5 show speed and torque-component current responses at reference speed of 3000 rpm, 300 rpm, 30 rpm, respectively. It is easy to see that overshoot in speed and torque-component current responses, and steady-state speed error E_{SS} for 1st method are much larger than those for 2nd method at simulated reference speeds as shown in Figures 3-5. The reason for this is that the integral constant time $T_{i\omega}$ of the 1st method is 2540 times longer than that of the 2nd method. Table 2 shows overshoot, undershoot due to load activation, E_{SS} , and stator current $i_{s\alpha}$ THD with advantages in overshoot, E_{SS} , THD for the 2nd method-proposed method. For undershoot, the 1st approach brings reduction of approximate 60% in comparison to the 2nd method. Figures 5 and 6 show that stator current responses of the 1st method fluctuate more than the 2nd one, especially at times of starting and change of load torque. This leads to THD of the 1st design approach significantly higher than the 2nd one.

Table 2. Performances of two PI speed controller design methods.

$\omega_{m,ref}$	Overshoot [rpm]		Undershoot [rpm]		Steady-state error [rpm]		Current THD [%]	
	1 st method	2 nd method	1 st method	2 nd method	1 st method	2 nd method	1 st method	2 nd method
3000	0.063	0.013	1.025	1.041	0.220	0.0005	1.07	1.07
300	0.544	0.034	0.398	0.955	0.211	0.0001	0.45	0.39
30	0.598	0.035	0.382	0.956	0.211	0.0002	1.33	0.23

Figure 3. Motor speeds (upper) and torque-component currents at $\omega_{m,ref} = 3000 \text{ rpm}$

Figure 4. Motor speeds (upper) and torque-component currents at $\omega_{m,ref} = 300$ rpm

Figure 5. Motor speeds (upper) and torque-component currents at $\omega_{m,ref} = 30$ rpm

Figure 6. Stator currents at $\omega_{m,ref} = 30$ rpm

4. CONCLUSION

The paper presents the application of zero-pole elimination and desired-transient-response-based methods in design of PI speed controller for FOC PMSM drive of a simplified model of an EV. The performances of drive system with two approaches were verified in simulation environment. The proposed desired-transient-response-based method provided higher performance with lower overshoot, smaller steady-state speed error, and reduction in stator current THD in comparison to zero-pole elimination method. However, robustness to load change of zero-pole elimination one is higher than the proposed one. Other advanced controllers can be utilized to achieve better performance.

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